

Ratios of infective to noninfective insects were 5:20 when they were injected with diseased leaves, 2:19 with diseased leaf sheaths, 1:21 with diseased roots, and 0:22 with diseased stems. The concentration of the virus seemed to be

higher in the leaves. Injection of sap from diseased plant leaves inoculated 10 days earlier gave a ratio of 1 to 13; 20 days earlier, 2:21; 30 days earlier, 4:20; 40 days earlier, 3:19; 50 days earlier, 1:17; and 60 days earlier, 1:22.

When injected with the sap of viruliferous insects 5 days after acquisition feeding, infective insects were 0:17; 10 days after, 0:18; 15 days after, 3:20; 20 days after, 4:12; 25 days after, 7:15; and 30 days after, 2:5. ■

Tungro incidence in Bihar and West Bengal, India

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A severe incidence of tungro virus disease occurred during 1981 kharif in parts of Bihar and West Bengal (see figure). Disease incidence was 40-100% in Bihar and 60-100% in West Bengal.

Transmission tests of samples collected from different locations were conducted to identify the virus. About 50 nonviruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* were confined on each sample for 48 hours, then on 10-day-old Taichung (Native) 1 seedlings for 24 hours. Typi-

cal symptoms of tungro virus developed within 7-10 days.

In North Bihar, the popular local variety Bakol was observed to be highly susceptible to tungro. Among the high-yielding semidwarf varieties grown in the area, Jaya, Pankaj, and Sita were susceptible; Rajendra Dhan 201 and Saket 4 were tolerant. Local improved variety BR34 was fairly tolerant. Disease incidence was higher in wetlands than in drylands.

In West Bengal, IR8, Jaya, and Mahsuri were highly susceptible to tungro. Local varieties Dorangi, Pankalash, Raghusail, and Patnai 23 were susceptible. A few local varieties — Mugh, Bismoni, Kartiksail, and Tillakachari — appeared resistant. ■

Rice gall dwarf virus occurrence in Peninsular Malaysia

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During a survey of rice virus disease incidence in January 1982, a number of rice plants showing characteristic symptoms of rice gall dwarf disease were observed at MARDI Rice Research Station, Bumbong Lima. The undersurface of leaf blades showed typical light green, almost round galls or vein-swelling (see figure). Infected plants were stunted, had fewer tillers, and appeared darker green than surrounding healthy plants.

A latex agglutination test used latex sensitized with antisera against rice gall dwarf virus prepared from a virus isolate from Thailand. A positive reaction showed that both viruses were serologically similar, confirming the presence of rice gall dwarf virus in Peninsular Malaysia. ■

Tungro outbreak in Bihar and West Bengal, India, in 1981.

Light green galls on undersurface of leaves of gall dwarf virus-infected rice plant.